

THE MEANING OF TERMINOLOGY. TERMS AND ITS FORM IN LINGUISTICS

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted the stages of terminology and its role in linguistic in which aims to identify structural features of linguistics terms in language. Moreover, it describes development of terminology and its origin meaning also what is the terminology itself

Key words: Terminology, development, 3 tips, structures, discourse, product, process, Term, terminological deviation, Terminological types, origin meaning.

Terminology is the branch of linguistics that studies and analyses terms, while lexicology focuses on the vocabulary (collection of words) of a language in general, and on the art of compiling, writing and editing dictionaries. The term has a singular or unambiguous tendency; the term has a clear, nominative function, to which emotionality, the meaning of the term, is equal to the concept; the term is stylistically neutral; terminological lexicon is a separate system. It also terminological vocabulary are words with a exceptional function. They can be called in various ways. However, it is with them that scientists operate in the process of interaction within various scientific spheres. In this particular metalanguage, old knowledge is fixed, and new knowledge is formed and fixed. It is a means of developing science and at the same time, represents a kind of reflection of the totality of scientific achievements in each specific field. This article examines the origin of sociolinguistics terms. In the existing scientific literature, this issue not received comprehensive coverage in unusual studies, there is no complete description of the relationship between native Russian terms and those borrowed from other languages, linguistic and extralinguistic factors of the appearance of borrowings in the system of sociolinguistics terms have not been disclosed.

The study of these issues undoubtedly contributes to the deepening of knowledge on all aspects of the sociolinguistic terminological field. This is important when studying the dynamics of the formation of the conceptual apparatus of this branch of science. New words appear and take root in the existing conceptual apparatus in the process of the interaction of languages. Borrowings depend on many factors: on the

nature and intensity of contacts with other languages, on the existing need for new terms in a particular science. (See more in L.P. Krysin[1]) To get a complete picture of the conceptual apparatus , it is vital to know the history of the origin of terms - this complements our views about the ways of science development .

Examining the germinal system of sociolinguistics in retrospect, it is easy to notice how it changes under the influence of time: the life of society changes, research is carried out, terms become obsolete and new ones replace them terminological borrowings continue in the process of studying foreign concepts and exchanging scientific experience . The terminological apparatus naturally meet the needs of the time. New words appear in the conceptual apparatus in the process of scientific research, and also come from other sciences or from other branches of linguistics. Both linguistic and extralinguistic factors played an special role in the formation of the Russian terminology of social linguistics

The extralinguistic factors considered in this article include the cultural and linguistic features of the Russian language, the formation of the written tradition of the metalanguage of socio - linguistics and the professionally conditioned contacts of scientists in this field [1] The etymological composition of the terminological system of Russian sociolinguistics is quite diverse . If there is a certain corpus of native Russian terms (20 %) (Table . 1) , yet a significant part of the special vocabulary of sociolinguistics is borrowed from other languages . This article is an attempt to trace the role that foreign language terms played in the formation of the conceptual apparatus.

Apart from this, Terminology is a group of specialized words and respective meanings in a particular field, also it is a discipline that studies, among other things, the development of such terms and their interrelationships within a specialized domain. Terminology plays an important role in the understanding of contexts and specialized texts. Understanding the intricate terminological details of the technical and scientific contexts helps students comprehend what the main message of the document

In terminology studies, naming is obviously a central issue, even an axiomatic concept. The most recent illustration of this importance is undoubtedly the monumental monograph by G. Petit (2009), which presents a large synoptic table of the linguistic issues of the name, highlighting the complementarities and oppositions between the lexicological and terminological approaches its reflection is the frame of reference of his entire study: despite a thorough analysis of certain founding texts of what used to be called the terminology of the Viennese school, This positioning, moreover perfectly justified, allowing a coherent and clear presentation of the question,

explains a certain number of biases, in particular the choice to consider that the terminological designation is above all a matter of the linguistic planning of the State.

Many linguists and terminologists insist on the cognitive dimension of terminology. Terminology is a discipline whose object is the theoretical study of the denominations of objects or concepts used by this or that field of knowledge, the functioning in the language of terminological units, as well as the problems of translation, classification and documentation that arise about them[1]. Terminology is also called the set of terms, rigorously defined,

A terminology is first and foremost a set of specialized terms relating to the same field of activity which has its own vocabulary: terminology for medicine, IT, sport, the navy, etc. The word terminology also designates an activity, the "art of identifying, analyzing and, if necessary, creating the vocabulary for a given technique, in a concrete operating situation, so as to meet the needs of expression of the 'user' to produce terms and definitions to designate the concepts and realities of a domain: recently it was necessary to create genome, cybercamera, biofuel, short message...

Terminology (or terminography) applies to specialized languages just as lexicography relates to general language. A notion, a definition, a term: this is the principle of development of all terminology; each new notion must be precisely defined and designated by a term, the most appropriate, the most telling, the clearest possible. It is close to translation, relying on the meaning of a concept to give equivalent terms from one language to another. with regard to its types terminology. Specialized expressions indigenous to a particular field, subject, trade, or subculture: argot, cant, dialect, idiom, jargon, language, lexicon, lingo, patois, vernacular, vocabulary.

Linguistic terms given in native language textbooks can be classified according to their formal structure as follows: 1. Simple terms 2. Compound terms 3. Pair terms 4.

Terms - compounds Simple terms. Simple terms belong to the horse family and have a core and formal spiritual integrity. For example: noun, adjective, number, possessive, connecting, mutq, homonym, synonym, metaphor, style, letter, text, sentence, comma, period, etc.

Simple terms are divided into simple primitive terms and simple artificial terms according to their derivational features: - simple primitive terms: language, speech, accent, term, dictionary, basis, verb. form, cut, possess, case, hyphen, quotation, allusion, synecdoche, norm, ratio, paronym, syllable, etc.

Simple artificial terms: linguistics, lexicography, invitation, greeting card, expressiveness, methodology, adjective, adverb, collection, writing, variation. Joint terms. Such terms are compound words consisting of more than one core combination.

This view of linguistic terms in native language textbooks belongs only to the mastered layer and is considered as a fundamental term in the Uzbek language: lexicology, lexicography, orthoepy, orthography ... A pair of terms.

Pair terms are formed based on the pairing of two words. During our research, we came across a single word-phrase pair. The term - compounds. As observed in all terminosystems, among our linguistic terms, the amount of term-compounds takes precedence.

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